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Mansehra Dolerite Deposit Assessment and Quarry Development Evaluation of Doga Sayyedana Site Higher Himalayas, North Pakistan

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Abstract: Being a part of Higher Himalayan region, Mansehra district and surrounding areas are always explored for the commercial mining due to its rich natural mineral resources. This study for the first time provides detail physical characterization of the Mansehra Dolerite, in order to calculate the potential reserves for the industrial and commercial use. Geochemical Laboratory test for the studied dolerite revealed that SiO₂ are highest lying between 47.03 and 48.64 (wt.%), while Al₂O₃ content varies from 13.8 wt.% to 15.21 wt.%. Iron (Fe₂O₃) ranges from 12.03 wt.% to 14.43 wt.% and MgO from 6.3 to 7.21 wt.%. TiO₂ content is low having a range of 0.77 – 1.95 wt.%. CaO composition ranges between 9.57 and 11.51 wt. %. Compositionally, Dolerite consists of fine to medium grained, anhedral to subhedral grain shape. The measured porosity is < 5%, hardness is 6.3 and specific gravity is 3.2. Whereas, the mechanical properties includes compressive strength i.e. ~13071 Psi which indicates its best usage for industrial purpose. On the surface, the body is extending over a length of about 80 to 100 meters. In order to reveal the potential reserve estimation, (Length x Width x Depth x Specific Gravity) formula is used. From six Quarries, total reserves of Quarry No 1, 2 and 3 is 1.15 Million Tons whereas for Quarry 4, 5 and 6 boulders are extracted giving the potential of 150 ton per month. Ratio of recovery from the mine is about 40 to 45% which is about 456750 Tons where as 30% of waste is used for the

production of cobbles, aggregate and for building materials. By using the advance techniques of mining one can enhance the production in the future.

Keywords: *Mansehra Dolerite, Reserve Estimation, Quarry Development, Higher Himalaya*

1. Introduction

Significant rise in demand of construction materials, it is important to carry out prospective research for the exploration of new resources and to estimate the reserves that are under construction. Igneous, metamorphic and sedimentary rocks are known to be as geological materials (Roberts et al., 1991). Same like granites that is commonly used as aggregate source (McNally, 2017), dolerite is also an important part of the construction industry. It is being used as dimension stone, flooring tiles and paving materials. All over the world dolerite is famous for kitchen counter tops due to its high strength and attractive quality polishing. The granitic rocks with variation of color, mineralogy, textural characteristics and mechanical properties occur in different parts of Pakistan but very few are being mined for construction purpose (Naeem et al., 2015). Mining of these deposits is very dependent on the accessibility. The purpose of this study is to undertake field visits to dimension stone (Dolerite Dykes, Market name “Black Granite”) deposits and quarries in Mansehra region, Higher Himalayas of north Pakistan (Fig. 1) , and to undertake assessment for technological up-gradation and model quarry development project for mechanized quarrying of dimension stone. In past, various consultant geologists and mining engineers visited the study area but there is no detail geological assessment report available for this economic deposit. Physical properties of Mansehra Granite were previously investigated by (Arif et al., 1999). The main objectives of the present study are to review of the studies done by the local consultants and selection of the most significant areas for model quarry/up gradation and also to conduct field visits and site inspections of the selected deposits/quarries for their assessment and evaluation. One of the key objectives is to define the potential market of the stone, estimating the mine-able reserves and evaluation of potential production capacity of the quarry.

2. Geology

A vast variety of Granitic rocks are exposed in different parts of Pakistan with the variation in texture, color, mineralogy, mechanical properties and specifically age. Mansehra granite is considered as one of the oldest granitic rock exposed in Pakistan. Geologically, the area between Mansehra, Oghi and Darband is generally overlain by Granite including Mansehra Granite, Hakale Granite, quartzite, Mansehra Dolerite, pegmatites and leucogranitic bodies (Ashraf, 1974; Shams, 1961). The major country rock unit (Mansehra

granite) is surrounded by Tanawal Formation of Neoproterozoic age (Baig et al., 1989) that has been intruded at places by dykes

Fig. 1. Satellite image of the study area.

like dolerite and also by pegmatite veins around the different location of study area. Mansehra granite comprises of medium to coarse-grained and porphyritic texture with K-feldspar phenocrysts. Variation in size and percentage of these phenocrysts can easily be observed in the field. The granite is massive but gneisses at some places in shear zones presented by stretched and augen shaped K-feldspar phenocrysts. Geochemical data for the granite show typical S-type characteristics. Zircon U–Pb dating yields $^{206}\text{Pb}/^{238}\text{U}$ crystallization ages of 483–476 Ma (Ogasawara et al., 2018). Previously Mansehra Granite was defined as of Cambrian age by Jan (1981) while using Rb/Sr method.

The dolerite (black granite) of present study occurs in the form of an elongated body intruding across the general strike of the enclosing rocks and is extending in the East West direction. The dyke on the surface has been concentrated into huge blocks measuring about 20-40 meters in thickness (Fig. 2) and around 100 m in length. Generally Mansehra dolerite is fine

grained jet black in color with small whitish spots and veins of feldspar were found in upper portion of the dyke. Olivine veins are found in lower portion of the dyke. Dolerite is principally comprised of 55 % plagioclase (labradorite), 35 % pyroxene (predominantly augite), 5 % biotite

Fig. 2.Thick bedded Dolerite beds.

and hornblende along with 5 % accessory minerals(Naeem et al., 2015; Shams, 1961). Quartzite in the studied area is composed of fine to medium-grained, fractured quartz grains with a wavy extinction which is the indication of effect of stress. These structural features includes E-W stretching nearly vertical dyke intruding granite and gneiss rocks and fracturing level Medium to high; no systematic pattern of fracturing could be observed from surface due to weathering. Fracturing density seems to increase in upper portion of dyke.

Plan showing the Lease Area of M/S Northern marble & Granite Pvt. Ltd. Near Village Doga Sayyedan Mansehra

Fig. 3. Map of the study area showing different quarry sites.

3. Methodology

To achieve the above objectives different field surveys have been conducted to know the geology of the study area. Inspection of all working quarries has been done in field to analyze fractures and variations in the mined stone. After the complete survey of total lease area, possibility of new sites has been indicated. A few fresh samples were collected from different quarry sites in order to conduct laboratory analysis in the Mineral Testing Laboratory at Peshawar. A detailed site map has been prepared on the scale of 1:12500 (Fig. 3).

Fig. 4.Dolerite boulders on surface at quarry 4 site.

4. Results

10 dolerite samples were selected for the geochemical analysis. Geochemical results of the samples have been presented in Table 01. The SiO₂ ratio of these rocks show a small variation having range between 47.03 and 48.64 wt.%. Al₂O₃ content varies from 13.8 wt.% to 15.21 wt.%. Iron (Fe₂O₃) ranges from 12.03wt.% to 14.43 wt.% and MgO from 6.3 to 7.21 wt.%. TiO₂ content is low having a range of 0.77 – 1.95 wt.%. CaO composition ranges between 9.57 and 11.51 wt. %. Generally, the studied Doleritic samples comprised of fine to medium grained, anhedral to subhedral grain shape. The measured porosity is < 5%, hardness 6.3 whereas the compressive strength is ~13071 Psi which is suitable for construction purpose. The specific gravity of the aforementioned Dolerite body is 3.2.

Table 1.Major oxides (wt. %) for the Dolerite rock samples.

Sample	MD04	MD07	MD08	MD10	MD13	MD23
Major Elements (%)						
SiO ₂	47.45	47.25	48.07	47.98	48.64	47.03
TiO ₂	1.95	1.02	0.87	0.77	0.87	1.42
Al ₂ O ₃	14.46	14.27	13.8	14.23	15.21	14.38
Fe ₂ O ₃	12.09	13.03	12.03	14.19	14.06	14.43
MnO	0.2	0.46	0.15	0.09	0.14	0.19
MgO	6.3	6.15	7.21	6.89	6.78	6.38

CaO	11.42	11.51	10.35	9.57	10.26	10.54
Na₂O	3.34	3.76	4.75	3.85	2.04	2.96
K₂O	1.33	1.46	1.03	0.9	0.97	1.21
P₂O₅	0.18	0.16	0.28	0.09	0.02	0.21

4.1 Reserve Estimation:

On the surface, the body is extending over a length of about 80 to 100 meters. The indicated reserve calculation can be made as two sides of the body are exposed, however the depth of the body can be taken approximately as 1/3 of the strike length as per usual practice in such type of ore reserve calculation. General formula for reserve estimation is (Length x Width x Depth x Specific Gravity). The specific gravity of the aforementioned Dolerite body is 3.2. Currently, Quarry 1, 2 and 3 are producing blocks while, Quarry 4, 5 and 6 are producing only boulders and the removal of overburden is in progress (Fig. 4).

After taking the various parameters, the reserves calculation of the dyke is made and shown in Table 2. Total reserve estimation done by adding reserves of Quarry No 1, 2 and 3 which is 1.15 Million Tons.

No.	Length (meter)	Width (meter)	Depth (meter)	Total Reserves (million tons)
Quarry # 1	80	40	50	0.51
Quarry # 2	100	25	30	0.24
Quarry # 3	100	25	50	0.4

Table 2. Total reserve estimation of quarry 1, 2 and 3.

Quarry 4, 5 and 6 are situated in a sequence and are of same type. In future these 3 quarries can be joined together to form a major quarry if proper beds will be found. These quarries are producing only boulders at present time. It will take about 2 years to reach proper beds.

Production of these quarries is 150 ton per month at present time.

4.2 Expected Recovery Of Reserves:

Same as international mines the ratio of recovery is about 40 to 45%.

Total estimated reserves = 1015000 Tons

Recovery @ 45% = 1015000 × 45% = 456750 Tons

- 10 % of blocks of standard dimension suitable for gang-saw cutting.

- 60 % of second choice blocks with some defector of smaller dimensions than standard.
- 30 % of waste, part of which is still recoverable for production of cobbles stone and building material.

Fig. 5.Semi block of Dolerite at mining site. Circle showing the In situ position of block.

5. Discussion

The extraction of commercial size blocks for the dimension stone are normally done by an open cut method known as quarrying. These quarrying methods include; use of various equipment that depends on the choice of dimension stone, size and shape of the deposit. The mining of the deposit has been started after properly studying the configuration of the dyke intrusion including structure, overburden etc. The quarrying work has been started in the form of “cutting up hills”, keeping in view the various parameters necessary for the mining/quarrying of the deposit.

At present time total six quarries are developed at study site of which five are productive. Two quarries are well developed and four small quarries are under development. Blocks, semi square blocks(Fig. 5) and boulders are further transported by means of big size trucks to the local granite cutting and polishing units established at various places with in the country for making big size granite tiles, slabs and other decorative. At present the recovery of sizeable granitic blocks is about 50 to 60% which would be increased to about 80% with the passage of time by adopting scientific techniques of quarrying. At present time total production is about 600 to 800 tons per month.

Physical properties like color, hardness etc. of Dolerite stone at study area is feasible for mining and to use in construction purpose. This mining project can be beneficial for local

community in terms of direct employment and Industrialization of under developed area would bring all associated benefits to local economy and social life. In broad term the Government would get the revenue in the shape of royalty, dead rent, excise duty etc. on the above mining project.

6. Conclusion

Considering the geotechnical properties of rocks exposed in the leased area of Doga Sayyedana the following conclusions are being made for further development of the mining activities at the project site.

- This deposit is suitable for the development of Scientific Quarries for small and medium scale production capacity of boulders, semi blocks and standard dimension blocks of good quality dolerite.
- Good National and International market for blocks of standard dimensions; Semi blocks and Boulder will be suitable for sale to local market.
- After proper investigation, various models of these dimension stones will be prepared and displayed country wise to create awareness among the people and specially the business community.
- The Dolerite body in the area occurs within a topography which is quite suitable for quarrying work and at time some more quarries can be developed.
- This study is of preliminary nature. However, it has delineated areas of interest for the investors.
- As quarry 4, 5 and 6 are producing boulders at present time and quarries are not completely opened, so in future after development of these quarries exact reserve estimation can be done.

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